

EBFMC25-OP-88 · Herpes Zoster Misdiagnosed as Irritant Contact Dermatitis and Treated with Steroids: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Herpes zoster ophthalmicus (HZO) is defined as the involvement of the ophthalmic branch (V1) of the fifth cranial nerve by herpes zoster.

Case Presentation: Although an HZO diagnosis does not always indicate ocular involvement, approximately 50% of cases develop ocular complications. It is typically characterized by a unilateral dermatomal distribution of erythematous and vesicular rashes, often accompanied by severe neuropathic pain.

Discussion: Ocular complications may include conjunctivitis, keratitis, episcleritis, scleritis, uveitis, secondary glaucoma, cataract, and retinal necrosis. HZO is often mistaken for conditions with similar skin findings, such as irritant contact dermatitis (ICD).

Conclusion: Misdiagnosis can lead to delayed treatment in HZO or unnecessary and potentially harmful therapy in ICD.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Herpes zoster, steroid, contact dermatitis

INTRODUCTION

Varicella-zoster virus (VZV) is a member of the Herpesviridae family and possesses an envelope and double-stranded deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) (Davis & Sheppard, 2019). VZV is highly contagious and can be transmitted via the respiratory route or through direct contact with vesicular lesions, leading to the primary infection known as chickenpox (Newman & Jhaveri, 2019; Patik, Goldust, & Wollina, 2022). The primary disease presents with cutaneous lesions in various stages of development. Vesicular lesions remain contagious until they crust over; the host is also considered contagious from 24–48 hours before the onset of the rash (Davis & Sheppard, 2019; Newman & Jhaveri, 2019). After the initial infection, the virus remains latent in sensory ganglia for an indeterminate period (Davis & Sheppard, 2019). Reactivation may occur due to immunosuppression caused by factors such as advanced age, physical trauma, psychological stress, malignancy, radiation therapy, transplantation, steroid treatment, and HIV infection, resulting in symptoms

characterized by unilateral radicular pain and vesicular rash in a dermatomal distribution (Joo, Lee, & Kim, 2019; Vineet et al., 2013).

Herpes zoster ophthalmicus (HZO) is defined as the herpes zoster involvement of the ophthalmic branch (V1) of the fifth cranial nerve. While an HZO diagnosis does not always include ocular findings, approximately 50% of cases present with ocular complications (Kedar, Jayagopal, & Berger, 2019). Ocular manifestations can be acute, chronic, or recurrent and may include conjunctivitis, keratitis, episcleritis, scleritis, uveitis, secondary glaucoma, cataract, and retinal necrosis (Liesegang, 2008). Contact dermatitis caused by plants or local topical medications may mimic HZO (Tuft, 2020). Therefore, differential diagnosis and treatment must be approached with caution. With early diagnosis and antiviral therapy, postherpetic neuralgia and ocular sequelae can be prevented; however, misdiagnosis or treatment delay may result in poor visual prognosis (Liesegang, 2008; Werner et al., 2017).

In this study, we present a case of HZO that worsened following steroid treatment administered after a misdiagnosis of irritant contact dermatitis.

CASE PRESENTATION

An 88-year-old male patient presented to the dermatology clinic with complaints of redness and painful, watery blisters around the left eye, one week after undergoing cataract surgery in the same eye. The pain was described as burning and sharp, radiating to the scalp. The patient reported marked cutaneous sensitivity in the affected area.

Considering the patient's recent surgical history and the use of a sterile ophthalmic drape over the left eye during phacoemulsification surgery (Figure 1), the dermatology clinic evaluated the lesions as irritant contact dermatitis.

Figure 1

The patient was administered 1 mg/kg intramuscular (IM) steroid and was prescribed a topical corticosteroid ointment to be applied twice daily to the lesions. Due to worsening of symptoms and progression of the skin lesions following treatment, the patient was referred to the ophthalmology department.

Grouped vesicular lesions with serous fluid and crusting were observed around the left eye, extending to the forehead. The severe pain in the area of the lesions radiated to the forehead and ear (Figure 2).

Figure 2

Best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) was 0.8 in both eyes. Intraocular pressure (IOP) was 18 mmHg in the right eye and 16 mmHg in the left eye. Anterior segment examination revealed normal conjunctiva and clear cornea in both eyes; both eyes were pseudophakic, and the anterior chambers appeared normal. Fundus examination showed normal optic discs and retinal findings bilaterally.

A diagnosis of herpes zoster was established, the existing topical corticosteroid therapy was discontinued, and the steroid ointment was gently removed from the skin without causing trauma. Following confirmation of normal renal function tests, the patient was started on oral valacyclovir 1000 mg three times daily, along with an oral non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), a vitamin complex, and proton pump inhibitor (PPI) therapy. Intravenous (IV) treatment was planned in case of non-response to oral therapy.

At the follow-up visit in the second week of treatment, the patient's symptoms had regressed, and the vesicles and crusting extending from the left periocular area to the forehead had completely resolved (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Oral valacyclovir therapy was continued at 1000 mg three times daily for a total of three weeks. The patient was closely monitored for a potential iridocyclitis episode following lesion resolution. As iridocyclitis did not develop, the patient was advised to return to the ophthalmology clinic if any new symptoms occurred.

DISCUSSION

Herpes zoster ophthalmicus (HZO) occurs in approximately 10–25% of herpes zoster cases (Shaikh & Ta, 2002), and ocular complications are estimated to develop in about 50% of these cases (Kedar, Jayagopal, & Berger, 2019). HZO typically presents as a unilateral, dermatomal distribution of erythematous and vesicular lesions, often accompanied by severe neuropathic pain (Liesegang, 2008; Vrcek, Choudhury, & Durairaj,

2017). Ocular complications can range from keratitis and anterior uveitis to scleritis and, in rare cases, panophthalmitis (Alkan Çeviker et al., 2019). In our case, the presentation was limited to cutaneous lesions, and no ocular involvement was observed.

Dermatological and infectious diseases affecting the periorbital region constitute an important aspect of ophthalmic practice. Among these, HZO and irritant contact dermatitis (ICD) may present with similar initial clinical features, making differential diagnosis challenging (Ergönül, 2017; Liesegang, 2008).

Particularly during the prodromal phase or when lesions present atypically in the early stages, HZO may be misdiagnosed as ICD, which shares similar cutaneous findings (Werner et al., 2017). ICD is a non-immunologic inflammatory response to environmental chemical, physical, or biological irritants. Due to its thin skin and exposure to external factors, the periorbital region is especially susceptible to ICD. Clinically, ICD presents with erythema, edema, burning sensation, and occasionally vesicular eruptions, which may resemble HZO (Papier, Tuttle, & Mahar, 2007).

In this case, the patient initially presented to the dermatology clinic with erythematous and edematous lesions in the periorbital area. Based on a preliminary diagnosis of irritant contact dermatitis, topical steroid therapy was initiated. However, due to a lack of improvement in symptoms, the patient was referred to the ophthalmology clinic, where a diagnosis of HZO was established. The delayed diagnosis of HZO led to a postponement in antiviral therapy, prolonging the disease course and intensifying the symptoms. Furthermore, the uncontrolled use of topical steroids in herpes virus infections may suppress the immune response, promote viral replication, and increase the risk of ocular complications (Liesegang, 2008; Werner et al., 2017).

Certain key features are critical in making the differential diagnosis. HZO typically presents unilaterally in a dermatomal pattern, often with vesicles, intense burning pain, and involvement of the nasociliary branch (Hutchinson's sign) (Alkan Çeviker et al., 2019; Vrcek, Choudhury, & Durairaj, 2017). This sign, which includes lesions on the tip of the nose, is considered a predictor of ocular involvement. On the other hand, ICD is usually bilateral or associated with a history of direct contact, and symptoms such as itching and stinging are more prominent (Papier, Tuttle, & Mahar, 2007). For diagnosis, Tzanck smear, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), or serologic testing may be used in suspected HZO, while the diagnosis of ICD is typically based on clinical evaluation and a history of exposure to irritants (Papier, Tuttle, & Mahar, 2007; Werner et al., 2017). Failure to make an accurate differential diagnosis may lead to delayed treatment in HZO or unnecessary and potentially harmful therapies in ICD.

This case highlights the importance of carefully assessing ocular involvement in patients presenting with dermatologic symptoms and considering viral etiologies in cases with unilateral, dermatomal rashes. In particular, a multidisciplinary approach enhances the accuracy and effectiveness of diagnosis and treatment in cases presenting with ophthalmic signs.

CONCLUSION

Herpes zoster ophthalmicus and irritant contact dermatitis are two conditions that may pose diagnostic challenges due to overlapping clinical features. However, an accurate diagnosis can be achieved through a thorough medical history, comprehensive dermatological and ophthalmological examination, and the use of appropriate laboratory tests. It is essential to recognize that delayed diagnosis and treatment of HZO may result in serious ocular complications, while ICD can be effectively managed with proper barrier precautions and topical therapy.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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